

Nigerian Teacher Education Reform: Implications for National Development

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Abstract

The paper maintains that the teacher plays an indispensable role in the advancement of national development and this necessitated Nigeria as a changing society, to embark on teacher education reform. With the reform, the teacher is meant to imbibe the spirit of the new Nigerian age; willing to share new information and skills with his educands, as well as with his fellow teachers; to seek more knowledge on his own initiatives without any fear of failure. The paper synthesizes the implications of Nigeria teacher education reform for national development and proposes some strategies for achieving a meaningful teacher education reform.

Key words: Education, Teacher, Reform, National Development

Introduction

The aims and objectives of education cannot be accomplished without the role of the teacher. Every country's educational system ought to be a means of providing the manpower at various levels of the economy on which modernization depends. A teacher is the architect who designs the superstructure on which education revolves. It is in accord with this assertion that, the Federal Government of Nigeria in its National Policy on Education offers a view-point that, "since no education system may rise above the quality of its teachers, teacher education shall continue to be given major emphasis in all educational planning and development" (FGN, 2004: 39).

To this end, Nigeria as a changing society embarks on its teacher education reform, which cannot be divorced from the role the teacher plays in the advancement of national development. On the part of Ezugwu (2001), it is only a competent teacher that can execute the important but onerous task of manipulating the child, and educational system to build the nation. Since there is logical and necessary relationship between the teacher, the educational system and the national development, Nigeria teacher education must not be treated as no man's land, where every old

woman plants mushroom anyhow. For this reason Nigeria teacher education reform is to aim at effecting an enduring improvement on the teachers and the existing educational system. Though changes are unavoidably due to the dynamic nature of the society as evident in innovations going on around the world, particularly with the use of computer, Internet services and other technological and electronic devices. Such reforms are not mere paper work but meant to be adequately implemented to enable the Nigerian teacher, whose task is to influence and make meaningful changes, in the life of his students and the society.

The Ideas that Informed Nigeria Teacher Education Reform

The general purpose of teacher education reform is to enable the teacher develop the skills and qualities that will increase his professional effectiveness. In Nigeria, the teacher in the assessment of Ogbonnaya (2003), constitutes the most important single category of high level or skilled-manpower requirement. The teacher is a citizen authorized for the improvement of the society. He is not only, a builder for he works with the higher and finer values of civilization. In the analysis of Stoff and Schwartzberg (2000), the teacher is perceived as a prophet who lays the foundation of tomorrow. He is a reformer who seeks for the means of removing the handicaps that weaken and destroy life, and he also has the legal role of *loco parentis*. Plato (427-347 BC) in his *Republic* (374Bg maintains that the services of teachers are vital for the welfare of the state and very individual. Beyond this, the nation's teachers directly influence the quantity and quality of the services provided by all the other professions.

The role of the teacher in any society as Adeyanju (2006), articulates, lies at the heart of its intellectual and social life, and it is through the teacher that each generation comes to ten TIS with its heritage, produces new knowledge, and learns to deal with change, provided the teacher has been well enough educated to act as the transforming element. The education of the teachers is at the nerve centre of the whole educational system, and if it fails to function there, the system fails. In relation to the above, there is need for proper teacher education reform to enable him do well in his professional practice. With the reform programme, the teacher has to enter into the spirit of the new Nigerian age, be willing to share new skills and information with his fellow teachers, seek more knowledge on his own initiative and above all, grow flexible and be willing to experiment without fear of failure.

Consequent on the above, the flexibility of such new or reformed teacher is to be built into his total professional and academic make-up. He is to be helped through regular in-service training to keep abreast of new techniques, skills and researches in his fields. Indeed, it is this idea that informed the Federal Government of Nigeria to state in its Education Policy Document that, "Teacher education shall continue to take cognizance of changes in methodology and in the curriculum. Teachers shall be regularly exposed to innovations in their profession" (FGN, 2004: 40). The essence of any country establishing school system, is to ensure sustainable social development in its society. The realization of such sustainable social development depends on the teacher and his products in the society.

In the same token of thought Okpala (2000) affirms in his research report that, an individual is considered educated if he is cultured, and contributing positively to the development of his society. Interpretatively, there is need to reform. Nigeria teacher education in order to expose both the teacher and the student teacher to a wealth of related cognitive knowledge and affective experience. The dictum is true that a poor teacher tells, while an average teacher informs; a good teacher teaches, while an excellent teacher inspires. The Nigerian school system is in dire need of excellent teachers to inspire confidence into the teaching profession in the country. The needed crop of excellent teachers can only be produced through effective teacher education programme. It is in this context that the Federal Government of Nigeria deems it wise to explicate the policy that would guide the Nigeria teacher education reform.

The Imperatives of the National Policy on Teacher Education Reform

The policy proposes that all teachers in the various levels of Nigeria educational system are to be professionally trained and qualified. The teaching profession is to be legalized, while the 'basic qualification for entry into the profession would be the National Certificate of Education (NCE). Those already engaged in teaching but not professionally qualified, shall be given a period of time within which to qualify for registration or leave the profession as regards the newly qualified teachers, they have to serve a period of one (1) year internship for degree holders, and two (2) years for NCE holders. Teaching services shall be so planned that teachers can transfer from state to state without loss of status. The policy, document in addition underscores that the goals of the teacher education reform should include:

1. producing highly motivated, conscious and efficient classroom teachers for all levels of our educational system;
2. encouraging further the spirit of enquiry and creativity in teachers;
3. helping teachers to fit into social life of the community and the society at large, and enhance their commitment to the national goals;
4. providing teachers with the intellectual and professional background adequate for their assignment and make them adaptable to changing situations; and
5. enhancing teachers' commitment to the teaching profession(FGN,2004:39-41).

The supra stated proposals on the teacher, education reform attest that Nigeria as an entity, has reached a new moment of decision in its national development. Teacher education in the words of Olukemi (2004), is the soul of every modern educational system, and a nation without a good teacher education, is in a moribund state. The growth of such a nation will be stunted, if not distorted. Arguably, the Nigeria teacher education reform proposals with its goals and promises have some implications for national development.

The Implications of Nigeria Teacher Education Reform for National Development

Based on the research report of Ifedi (2003), Transparency International (TI) group affirmed that Nigeria is the second most corrupt country after Bangladesh. The Nigerian schools at all levels are now infested with indiscipline, and general moral laxity. Laziness, stealing and

violence have become common place. In the larger society, materialism and armed robbery have escalated. A significant dimension of these maladies in the view of Okafor (1991) can be traced back to the way teachers are trained, and what teachers teach their pupils by word and example. Certainly, the pathetic condition of our Nigerian experience as Okafor (1994) further points out, has not given any credibility to our national development. Such caustic commentary suggests the exigency of Nigeria teacher education reform.

It is a *contradiction in adjecto* (contradiction in terms) for the government to claim in its teacher education reform proposal that it would produce highly motivated and efficient *classroom* teachers; enable teachers to fit into social life of the community; enhance their commitment to national goals and teaching profession, while their salaries and entitlements are not given to them as and at when due. Sad enough, the very government the teachers are serving, has taken the lead to reduce and ridicule the teachers as people of no image. For instance the issue of harmonization of teachers' condition of service and promotion opportunities are treated with levity of mind. Occasionally, the teachers have to go on strike before the government attends to their legitimate demand. Many a teacher have given out the fullness of themselves, and they are retired with gratuity and pension privileges that take donkey years to materialize. These retired heroes are abandoned by the government to was the away in penury and wretchedness. To this cause Abiogu (2004) reiterates that a hungry teacher, a teacher on strike, and a half-baked teacher would not be prepared to make sacrifices required to rescue the nation from the precipice into which it is drifting. The Nigeria teacher education reform, proposal, includes providing teachers with the intellectual and professional background adequate to changing situations, but in our educational institutions today, there are a lot of mediocre and non-performers. These nonprofessionals or those who are educated but they are not experts in their field of practice, and poor teachers have caused quantum damage in the teaching exercise due to lack of training in teaching methodology. Such teachers who are lacking in knowledge, skills and experience cannot strive to achieve the goals and philosophy of our national development.

The issue of teachers being transferred freely from place to place without loss of status, has ever remained a plausible theory. The problem as Ogbonnaya (2003) identifies it, stems up from the attitude of some education administrators and planners, who are always ready to receive bribes from teachers so that their transfers can be effected. Some 'states are presently lacking qualified teachers, while others have a surplus. The sending out of the surplus is not possible unless on very few cases if any. It is never done as a matter of routine. Some teachers who agreed to be posted to new areas where they are needed most, also suffer a lot in the sense that they will receive lower salary than what was their former salary scale (Ogbonnaya, 2000). This type of dishonorable craft is destructive to our national development in the comity of developed nations. When a country educates a lawyer, an engineer or a medical doctor, it has only educated some individuals, but if it educates a teacher, it has educated a nation. For instance, the history of development of any nation is tied to the history of its educational development. The industrial revolution in Europe and the technological advancement in Japan and America were the products of their functional and productive education systems. This is why Nigeria and other countries

worldwide, hopefully expect their educational sector to provide them with medical 'doctors, nurses, engineers, teachers, scientists, technologists, clergymen and other professionals whose intelligence could be utilized to solve societal problems, such as: poverty, ignorance, hunger, shelter, epidemics, unemployment and what have you. It is therefore logical to infer that the neglect of any country's teacher education development programme would have a disastrous effect in the national development of such a nation. The reason for this is that effective education of the teacher implies effective training of manpower resources, which is a starting point in any country's onward march, towards achieving sound national development.

Strategies for Achieving Teacher Education Reform a Meaningful Teacher Education Reform

Based on this paper's discussion and its implications for national development, the following strategies are hereby articulated for meaningful teacher education reform:

1. teachers are creators of other professions, and the government must do everything within its power to ensure that the teaching profession is revitalized and brought back to its old glory, while the teachers are to accept their profession as a life mission, before more harm is done to our educational system which is the base of our national development.
2. the rule that the NCE will become the minimum qualification in the teaching profession in Nigeria, does not make teaching equal to those other professions. It is only when a university degree in education is made the minimum qualification, that teachers can earn confidence and parity of esteem.
3. this does not mean that the NCE holders, are to be dismissed from the school system. They could be given some date-line to up-date their qualification through in service training.
4. Student teachers should be assigned not only to one teacher, but to various subject teachers as mentors in their practicing schools. These teachers are to assess the student teachers. This is how the student teachers can build up their self confidence, as well as perfecting their professional skills.
5. the emphasis of the National Policy Document on teacher education reform, is more on teacher's academic education than on his preparation for teaching. There should be a balance of emphasize so as not to emphasize the teacher's academic education to the detriment of his teaching preparation.
6. the Nigerian teacher should feel free to transfer to any part of the country with cogent reasons. However, to ensure that teachers are not selective on where to teach, teachers in remote areas should be paid inconvenience allowance as it is done in some other professions.
7. the teacher must use his teaching and code of conduct to inspire his educands, bearing in mind that it is not only in chemical laboratory alone that wrong labeling can lead to serious disaster and death. It could also happen in the education process. The only difference is that in the later, it tends to be insidious and delayed, although instant effects have been known to occur.

8. the conditions of service of teachers must be reviewed to enhance their self-esteem. In addition to better and regular payment of salaries and allowances, the government is to create promotion opportunities at every educational level to allow for professional growth *at* each level. Qualification of teachers are to be considered in their salary structure. No matter how expensive education may seem, ignorance is more expensive.
9. improved living conditions for retired teachers should be pursued as a matter, of urgency, by any responsible government. The practice of abandoning them to waste away in penury and wretchedness, is not only treacherous but a rape of justice.

Conclusion

No nation has ever become great which had failed to give adequate attention to its school system, where the teacher is a strong catalyst to the child who grows to become a bundle of possibilities, in the upward development of the nation. The Nigeria teacher education reform is therefore a worthwhile venture, because a good teacher makes a good school, a good school makes a good scholar, while good scholars make a good nation.

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